

**THE IMPORTANCE OF IT TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING
SPEAKING SKILL TO B1 LEVEL STUDENTS**

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to IT technologies used in teaching English to B1 level students. The authors consider the role of digitalization in teaching, and also studied methods for introducing advanced technologies during practical classes and lectures. In the course of scientific and technological progress, complex changes in the economy, politics and society are integrated. Any global changes also have an impact on education. The development of IT technologies has accelerated the introduction of information technology into the educational process, thereby introducing changes in teaching methods.*

Key words: *IT technologies, digitalization, development, methodology, information, communication, language, traditional.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена ИТ-технологиям, используемым в обучении английскому языку студентов уровня В1. Авторы рассматривают роль цифровизации в обучении, а также изучают методы внедрения передовых технологий на практических занятиях и лекциях. В ходе научно-технического прогресса интегрируются сложные изменения в экономике, политике и обществе. Любые глобальные изменения также оказывают влияние на образование. Развитие ИТ-технологий ускорило внедрение информационных технологий в образовательный процесс, тем самым внося изменения в методы обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *ИТ-технологии, цифровизация, развитие, методология, информация, коммуникация, язык, традиционный.*

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at school is mastering foreign language communicative competence. Learning to speak in a foreign language is learning to express your thoughts orally, that is, speaking as a means of communication. Nowadays, knowledge of English is becoming an integral part of our lives. English is considered the language of international communication. However, the authors of the modern state educational standard put forward a different understanding of the purpose of teaching a foreign language in schools, mostly focusing B1 level students - the formation of communicative competence.

The school learning process is focused on practical knowledge of a foreign language and, as a result, great importance is attached to the problem of understanding foreign speech by ear. Recently, methodologists are increasingly turning their attention to the problem of listening. Although theoretical research is

being carried out in the study of this process, the practical application of certain teaching methods is not yet great.

It is widely known that the methodology for teaching listening comprehension is the least developed. The main reason is precisely the fact that until recently listening was considered a fairly simple skill. It was also believed that if, when teaching oral speech, the teacher pays full attention to speaking and helps them master this skill, then the students will learn to understand speech without additional preparation. The inconsistency of this opinion has been proven both in theory and in practice.[2-12]

The professionalism of a modern teacher is also determined by the skills of conveying information using information and communication technology tools. The process of teaching English in higher educational institutions must meet the trends in the training of highly qualified specialists. This process is inseparably linked with the introduction of advanced technologies and means of communication into human life. The authors note both negative and positive aspects of informatization of higher education, which manifested themselves especially clearly during the poke-down and the use of distance learning technologies.

The continuous process of modernization of the higher education system affects linguistic areas, which, in particular, entails high demands on the teaching of English. The teacher must introduce new information technologies in teaching English and compare them with the teaching load, goals and objectives. In modern higher education, information technology methods are actively used and language training is being improved. Along with traditional educational programs in higher educational institutions, there is an innovative and technological pedagogical component in the process of teaching foreign languages, in particular English.

The process of introducing information technology into education is called informatization of education. Today, a professional foreign language teacher must be able to convey the material using new modern information and communication technological methods, and be able to work with students using distance education technologies [6., 107].

The development of electronic media has led to a “COM-computer-mediated” form of communication in higher education. In learning English, it is necessary to continue to use network interaction and online means of communication based on software that supports video telephony, video conferencing, broadcasting educational resources, etc.

In secondary school, mainly two types of audio texts are used - descriptive text and plot text. In the practice of learning foreign languages, listening texts must be authentic, accessible in content and linguistic composition, short in length, and mostly monothematic.

Based on the specifics of listening as one of the most difficult types of speech activity, it is important first of all to know the main difficulties of mastering it.

Language difficulties:

1.Features of the act of listening and speech activity listener's ability (wide range of topics, rich lexical material, fairly fast pace of speech).

2.Peculiarities of speech of native speakers (differences in spoken and written speech, authentic texts and educational texts, different styles).

Cultural difficulties:

Sociolinguistic and sociocultural component, communicative competence (the language must be studied in the context of a particular culture).

Successful mastery of listening involves removing or overcoming its difficulties.

Internet information resources provide in-depth language learning. The modern world is permeated with flows of information, and society is increasingly called information society due to the intensive informatization of all types of human activity. The introduction of informatization in education is one of the first places in reforming the education system. Today it is important for teachers to understand the role of informatization in the modern world. Computerization of many areas today has shown our society the required level of foreign language proficiency, the conditions for its use, for example, in telecommunication networks, where the ability to communicate in writing and orally without intermediaries is very important. The main goal of using digital technologies in schools today is to prepare the new generation for a full life in the information society, improving the quality of accessibility and effectiveness of education. [5.,31]

Informatization of secondary schools is an integral part of the informatization of education.

Digital technologies in teaching a foreign language at school have a number of advantages: students perceive and remember the material better; economical use of time; individualization of training, determination of the depth and sequence of assimilation, pace of work; intensification of training and increasing the level of motivation.

Thus, based on the theoretical and practical research of this problem, it can be stated that the hypothesis of this study has been proven.

The use of digital technologies in the process of teaching listening as a type of speech activity to secondary school students is truly advisable.

The use of digital technologies in the educational process makes it possible to provide most students with:

- achieving the program level of listening skills and abilities;
- formation, development of internal and external motivation for learning;

It can also be argued that the use of new information technologies in teaching does not exclude traditional technologies, however, it is new information technologies that become the main means of access to various sources of information, which is one of the most important aspects of the modern educational process.

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